

SECURITY MARKET OVERVIEW: EUROSATORY 2024 SECURITY & DEFENCE EVENT

Main Authors

Guillaume Brumter (EOS)
Cyril Piotrowicz (FRMDLI)

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About ENACT

ENACT is a knowledge network focused on the fight against crime and terrorism (FCT). The network is funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme in Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society. The project addresses the call topic HORIZON-CL3-2022-SSRI-01-02 ‘Knowledge Networks for Security Research & Innovation’, aiming to collect, aggregate, process, disseminate and make the most of the existing knowledge in the FCT area.

The project aims to satisfy two major ambitions,

- Provide evidence-based support to the decision-makers in the EU research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the FCT domain, targeted explicitly at enabling more effective and efficient programming of EU-funded R&I for the fight against crime and terrorism.
- Act as a catalyst for the uptake of innovation by enhancing the visibility and reliability of innovative FCT security solutions.

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Acronyms

AR	Analytical Report
B2B	Business-to-Business
CBRN	Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
CERIS	Community of European R&I for Security
D&S	Defence and Security
EEN	Enterprise Europe Network
EU	European Union
FCT	Fight against Crime and Terrorism
FR	Flash Report
GICAT	Groupement des Industriels français de défense et de sécurité terrestre et aéroterrestre (the French Land Defence and Security Industry Association)
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
NCT	Non-conventional threat
PPE	Personal Protection Equipment
R&D&I	Research, Development and Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

EUROSATORY 2024: Overview

The EUROSATORY [1] exhibition is the global land and air benchmark event for Defence and Security (D&S) professionals. The 2024 edition of this event gathered over 2,000 exhibitors from 61 countries, 120 conferences and over 40,000 visitors, ahead of RSA Conference [2] in the United States of America (600 exhibitors and 40,000 visitors) and Security Asia [3] (250 exhibitors and 50,000 visitors). This event is organized by the Group of French Industries for Land and Air-Land Defence and Security (GICAT) [4], an association gathering more than 300 large groups, small-medium enterprises (SMEs) and start-ups.

Similarly to other security events, such as SICUR, TECNOSEC and DRONEXPO, which ENACT actively tracks to produce flash reports [5], the scale of EUROSATORY event fosters worldwide cooperation and attracts significant investments from governments and industries. The event also offers a platform for smaller businesses and research centres to showcase innovative solutions. This event does not include academic exhibitors, featuring primarily military and defence organisations and industries focused on innovations for D&S sectors.

For this 2024 edition, the exhibition revolved around 12 technology clusters [6] aiming to foster cooperation and ease the targeting of relevant exhibitors:

Table 1 - The technology clusters exhibited at Eurosatory 2024

Research, Tests and Measurement	Training and Simulation
Civil Security and Firefighting	Medical Cluster
Technologies for Infrastructure Security	NCT CBRNe
Engineering and Manufacturing	Cyber
Human Support and Logistics	Intelligence
Drones and Robotics	Embedded Electronics

[1] <https://www.EUROSATORY.com/en/>

[2] <https://www.rsaconference.com/>

[3] <https://www.securityasia.com.pk/>

[4] <http://www.gicat.com/en/home-page/>

[5] <https://enact-eu.net/results/>

[6] <https://www.EUROSATORY.com/en/trends/technology-clusters/>

In the same time, 120 Conferences featuring over 450 experts' speakers, about 17 key-topics mixing both technological and organizational stakes:

Table 2 - The key topics exhibited at Eurosatory 2024

Innovation	Disruptive technologies	Economy, Politics, and Financing
Defence Cooperation	Defence Helicopters	UAS/UAV and Counter-Drone Systems
Sustainable Defence	Armored Vehicles & Mobility	Air and Missile Defence Systems
Cybersecurity	Supply Chain Resilience	Autonomous Systems & Robotics
Space Capabilities	HELPED: Civil protection	Artificial Intelligence (AI) and ML
Logistics & Support		HR Challenges & Talent Management

EUROSATORY is a flag-event with 355 official delegations from over 90 countries and is heavily supported by the French Government with 4 ministries being exhibitors (Ministry of Armed Forces, Ministry of Interior, Ministry of European and Foreign Affairs and Ministry of Ecology) and every public agency present: National Police, National Gendarmerie, Firefighter, Armed Forces, Defence Innovation Agency, Transport Innovation Agency, etc.

A view on the Security Market

The 2024 edition of EUROSATORY hosted over 2000 exhibitors from more than 60 countries, attracting an estimated 76,000 professional visitors from the global D&S sectors.

With 40% of its exhibitors not being tied only to the defence industry, but also to the security community, EUROSATORY is not only about defence, armoured vehicles and external military operations. It's also interesting to underline that 12% of company are dedicated to the security and law enforcement market.

As ENACT focuses on technologies, innovations and research addressing FCT challenges, the following report considers only EUROSATORY exhibitors involved in producing solutions for the security or security and defence (such as dual-use technologies) domains.

For the purpose of this report, correspondences between the EUROSATORY activities classification (Annex 1), exhibitors activities description from their stand or website, and EU civil security (EUCS) taxonomy [7] were looked into.

[7] https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/ceris-community-european-research-and-innovation-security/eu-security-market-study/eu-civil-security-taxonomy-and-taxonomy-explorer_en

EUROSATORY 2024: Exhibitors products and services

EUROSATORY 2024 exhibition bring together the leading technology companies in the sectors of land, air-land defence and security, comprehensively displaying technologies, products and services across several application domains. Such as highlighted in the TECNOSEC and DroneExpo Flash Report [8], and in connection with lessons learnt in recent conflicts, attention was given to Unmanned Systems and Navigation and Surveillance as well as counter drones' technologies.

Figure 1. provides the distribution of exhibitors across the EUCS Taxonomy in the Functions domain, highlighting focus areas in descending order of importance, measured by their frequency of occurrence. This distribution reflects a broad spectrum of priorities in D&S operations. Mobility and Deployability leads with over 700 entries, underscoring the critical need for rapid movement and deployment in defence operations. Training and Exercises, Personal and Other Equipment for Prevention, Response, and Protection and Decontamination and Neutralization also feature prominently, reflecting the focus on preparedness, hazard mitigation, and crisis management. Areas like Monitoring and Surveillance and Data, Information & Intelligence Gathering show the increasing reliance on data-driven technologies in security. At the bottom of the list, Identification and Authentication of Persons, Assets and Goods and Investigation and Forensics, each with fewer than 100 units, suggest a more focused, possibly niche application within the overall operational structure.

FCT Functions

Figure 1 - Mapping of the exhibitors in the Functions domain, according to the EU Security Market taxonomy

[8] <https://enact-eu.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/ENACT-FLASH-REPORT-2-TECNOSEC-EVENT.pdf>

As regard to the EUCS Taxonomy technology areas (Figure 2), General Equipment stands out as the most represented category, with close to 950 entries, indicating its broad utility across different sectors. Training & Simulation follows with about 600 entries, emphasizing the importance of preparation and skill development in security operations.

Other significant categories include Critical Communications, Interoperable Communications and PPE/Safety Equipment, Surveillance Systems, and Healthcare/Medical Equipment, highlighting the growing focus on reliable communication networks and protective gear. Minimal attention is given to Data Analytics, Facilitation Systems and Secure Databases, and Internet-based Investigation, indicating these areas might be secondary in importance or have a more niche application. At the very bottom, Digital Forensics has the least focus, despite being a major are for security and law enforcement.

Overall, this distribution reflects a clear prioritization of basic operational equipment, safety, and communication over more specialized or analytical technologies.

Technology Areas

Figure 2 - Mapping of the exhibitors in the Technology domain, according to the EU Security Market taxonomy

EUROSATORY 2024 exhibitors' geographical distribution

The following section looks into the distribution of exhibitors across EU Member States and compares their participation to non-EU exhibitors.

European countries dominate the data, contributing a significant portion of the exhibitors. Outside the EU territory, there is notable representation from regions such as North America and Asia, with a smaller presence from the Middle East and Africa. This distribution suggests strong global interest in security technologies, with Europe leading the way in innovation and adoption, followed by significant engagement from other key global markets. The strong representation of EU D&S solutions providers can be explained as EUROSATORY focuses on addressing European D&S challenges and especially French companies, considering the organizer of the event is the GICAT.

Figure 3 shows the number of exhibitors from EU countries, represented by their country codes. France (FR) has the highest number of exhibitors, with 367, significantly more than any other country. Germany (DE) follows, with 98 exhibitors, and Italy (IT) comes third, with 28 exhibitors. Other countries with notable participation include Spain (ES) with 22 exhibitors, Sweden (SE) with 24 exhibitors and Austria (AT) and the Czech Republic (CE) with 18 and 17 exhibitors, respectively. Countries with relatively low participation include Portugal (PT) with just 3 exhibitors, followed by Cyprus (CY) with 4, and Luxembourg (LU), Slovenia (SI), Estonia (EE), Hungary (HU), and Slovakia (SK), all with 6 to 7 exhibitors.

These numbers show that Western European countries (France, Germany, Italy, Spain) have much higher exhibitor counts compared to Eastern European and smaller countries.

Figure 3 - Distribution of exhibitors from EU Member States, according to their country of origin

Figure 4 shows the geographical distribution of exhibitors from the EU and around the world, according to their country of origin.

USA stands out with the most exhibitors, totalling 95. This is significantly higher than any other country listed, suggesting either a significant economic or industrial focus in this exhibition. Australia (AUS) follows with 36 exhibitors, showing strong participation and China (CHN) is also prominent with 34 exhibitors, ranking third.

Countries with moderate participation include United Kingdom (GB) with 22 exhibitors, Turkey (TR) with 15 exhibitors, Canada (CA) with 14 exhibitors, India (IN) and South Korea (KR) both with 12 exhibitors. Norway (NO) had 10 representatives and Brazil (BR) and United Arab Emirates (AE) had both with 9 exhibitors.

Several countries have lower exhibitors, in the range of 1 to 4 exhibitors. Armenia (AM), Bosnia and Herzegovina (BA) had 4 exhibitors each, Pakistan (PK) with 2 exhibitors. EU companies have the highest number of exhibitors, with 690, which is much larger than any region listed.

Figure 4 – Geographical distribution of exhibitors from the EU and around the world, according to their country of origin

Relevant insights

EUROSATORY 2024 is recognised as one of the world's largest D&S exhibitions, bringing together a significant number of exhibitors and visitors from more than 60 countries. The event underscores Europe's leadership in security innovation, focusing on addressing both European and global D&S needs.

Exhibitors displayed several solutions to D&S actors, with a strong emphasis on the following FCT functions: Mobility and Deployability comes at the first function, followed by Training and Exercises and Personal and Other Equipment for Prevention, Response, and Protection. Looking into the EUCS Technology areas, technologies on General Equipment were the most represented, followed by Training & Simulation. Regarding these technologies, plurality of providers, from many countries is a factor to take into account regarding Horizon Scanning and Technology Scouting, implying both a high Technology Readiness Level and competitiveness on the market.

In terms of exhibitor participation, France dominates, far surpassing other countries like Germany and Italy. This reflects the centrality of France and broader Western Europe in the D&S sectors. Among non-EU countries, USA had the largest presence, followed by Australia, China, and UK. This distribution highlights strong global interest in the event, with Europe leading in innovation, while North America and Asia show significant engagement. Smaller contributions from regions like the Middle East and Africa suggest a more focused, albeit less dominant, presence at the exhibition.

When comparing with the TECNOSEC and SICUR Flash Reports' findings across the technology areas and FCT functions, the products and services presented at EUROSATORY differ in several ways. From the FCT functions perspective, Training and Exercises and Decontamination and Neutralisation appear among the five highest priorities while missing in TECNOSEC and SICUR exhibitions. On the other hand, the Monitoring and Surveillance of Environments and Activities FCT Function is a common priority across the three exhibitions. As regard to the Technology domains, EUROSATORY introduces two new priorities: Training and Simulation, and Guarding and Physical Protection (Non-Human) in the five most occurrent technology dimensions. Similarly to the FCT functions, the three exhibitions identified Critical and Interoperable Communications, and PPE / Safety Equipment as key technologies.

In comparison to the FCT R&I Priorities [9], the products and services displayed during EUROSATORY are not following the FCT R&I priorities. Indeed, only one function, Training and Exercises, is present in the top three functions FCT priorities. From a technological perspective, the highest-ranked technology dimension represented at EUROSATORY is in fourth position in the FCT priorities.

Regarding these exhibitors' nationality, ENACT will be able to better identify the specialties of each country, which may indicate state or institutional support in these fields, and therefore be weak signals of national priorities concerning a criminal or technological trend.

EUROSATORY 2024 reference information

Name of the event: EUROSATORY 2024, Protect your future, The global event for Defence and Security

Dates: 8 May – 9 May 2024

Location: Paris Nord Villepinte exhibition centre, ZAC Paris Nord 2, 93420 Villepinte – France (Halls 5a – 5b – 6)

Website: <https://www.EUROSATORY.com/en/>

[9] FCT R&I: An analysis of EU priorities 2014 – 2024: <https://enact-eu.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/ENACT-Analytical-Report-01-FCT-RI-An-analysis-of-EU-priorities-2014-2024.pdf>

APPENDIX A - EUROSATORY Areas of exhibition

Activity Areas	Sub-areas
Communication & Information Systems	Antennas - Masts - Dishes
	Command, Control, Communication & Information (C3I), Centres and Security Networks
	Computer - Terminal Access Units - Personal Digital Assistant (PDA)
	Connectics, Cables and Optical Fibers
	Cyber Defence - Electronic Warfare (Encryption, Countermeasure, Forensic Communication)
	Cybersecurity
	Data and Image Handling Systems
	Electronic Components
	Emergency Communication Systems
	Energy Systems: Batteries, Accumulators, Solar Panels...
	Intercoms, Phones, Headsets
	Optical and Electro-Optical Components
	Peripherals & Memory Storage
	Radios / Software Defined Radios (SDR)
	Satellite Communications (Networks, terminals and Broadcast)
	Detection, Location, Acquisition & Deception
Detection and Warning Systems - Countermeasures (Soft-Kill and Hard-Kill)	
Geographical Information System - Position Finding - Navigation (GPS) - Geolocation	
Identification Friend or Foe (IFF), Emergency Beacon	
Jamming	
Listening Devices	
Meteorological Measuring Means	
People and Vehicles Tracking Devices	
Radar Surveillance	
Sighting / Aiming Systems, Fire-Control Systems, Laser Range Finding (LRF)	
Signature Management (Acoustic, Thermal, Electromagnetic)	
Disaster, Business Continuity & Homeland Security	Acoustic Hailing Devices, Green Lasers
	Aseismic Equipment
	CBRN Warning systems
	Clearing, Lifting, Cutting and Digging Equipment
	Communication and Information tools in case of Disasters
	Crowd and Individuals Control (handcuffs...)

Activity Areas	Sub-areas
	Dematerialization of documents Disaster Medical Assistance Team (DMAT) Equipment Early Warning Systems for Natural Disaster Emergency Evacuation Systems (beacon, lighting, sirens...) Forensic Localisation Systems for Relief and Rescue Means of Preventing Human Errors Means to combat counterfeiting Measurement Means for Earthquake and Volcano Mobile Network Pollution Prevention and Control Pumps for Flood Rescue Kit for Relief Resuscitation Equipment (AED, oxygen masks...) Riot Control Equipment - Fences Telecommuting Weather Information Services - WIS
Field Preparation - EOD	Crossing Means (Bridge Layers, Bridging, Ferries...) Excavation and Earthmoving Flood Barriers and Equipment (Water Tube, Sandbag, Pumps...) Ground Trafficability - Matting Manual Mine Clearance - Explosive Containments Mechanical Demining Minefield Breaching - Line Charges Signs, Delineators, Marking Site Remediation Unexploded Ordnance (UXO) and Improvised Explosive Device (IEDs): Means for Detection and Destruction
Ground, Aerial & Naval Vehicles, Aircrafts and Boats	Aerostats, Balloons Aircraft - Reconnaissance and Surveillance Aircraft - Aerostats and Operating Equipment Ambulances and Sanitary Vehicles Boats, Patrol Boats, Rapid Response Boats, Vessels Crowd Control and Anti-riot Vehicles, Cash In Transit Vehicles Firefighting Vehicles Helicopters Hovercraft Light Armoured and Unarmoured Vehicles < 8 tons Logistic vehicles - Trucks - Trailers Motorcycles - Quads Parachuting and Air Delivery

Activity Areas	Sub-areas
	Helmets, Visors, Masks, Ear and Eye Protection Individual Protective Equipment and Devices (CBRNe) Miscellaneous Equipment (Lamps...) Survival Equipment Tactical Jackets - Rucksacks - Pouches - Holsters Technical Textiles (Against Fire, Medical, Smart...)
Infrastructures protection	Access and Entry Control - Detection of Hazardous Material and Items (Gate, X-ray, Scanner...) Armoured Rooms - Openings and Closings Systems (Locks...) - Safety Cabinets Aspiration - Smoke Clearing - Fireproofing - Weatherstripping Bastions, Fences, Barbed Wire, Sentry Box, Barriers, Bollards Biometric Identification Camouflage Fire Detection and Extinguisher Devices Screening Equipment (alcohol, narcotics...) Video Surveillance and Monitoring (Camera, Image Processing, Remote Control Equipment...)
Logistics for Operations - Installations	Camp Accommodation - Tents - Shelters - Temporary Installations CBRN Collective Protection (COLPRO) CBRN Decontamination Conditioning and Packaging (Cases...) Field Kitchens - Catering Equipment - Food Fire Detection and Alarm Systems (smoke, gas, heat detectors...) Generating Sets and Power Supply Systems Handling Equipment - Cranes - Repair Means Power Transportation, Distribution and Regulation Power, Lighting, Heating, Air-Conditioning Sanitary Amenities Storage - Resupply - Tagging / Bar Coding Treatment, Conditioning, and Storage of Water Warehouses - Installations
Medical & Emergency	First Aid and Role 1 Equipment Identification, Classification and Casualty Evacuation Medical and Surgical Equipment Mobile and Field Hospitals Protective Clothing (masks, gloves...) Purification - Pest Control - Decontamination Rescue Equipment and Desincarceration Means
Personal Equipment	Body Armor, Inserts and Protections Ceremonial Equipment - Medals - Uniforms Climbing Gear, Ladders and Hooks Clothing (Hairdressing, Belts, Underwear, Gloves, Shoes...) Decontamination Systems (CBRNe) Detection and Identification Systems (CBRNe) Diving Equipment

Activity Areas	Sub-areas
	Submarines
	Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) / Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) and Equipment
	Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGV) and Systems
	Unmanned Underwater Vehicle (UUV) / Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USV) and Equipment
	Up to 8 Tons Armoured Vehicles
	Upgrading Vehicles, Aircrafts & Boats
Infrastructures protection	Access and Entry Control - Detection of Hazardous Material and Items (Gate, X-ray, Scanner...)
	Armoured Rooms - Openings and Closings Systems (Locks...) - Safety Cabinets
	Aspiration - Smoke Clearing - Fireproofing - Weatherstripping
	Bastions, Fences, Barbed Wire, Sentry Box, Barriers, Bollards
	Biometric Identification
	Camouflage
	Fire Detection and Extinguisher Devices
	Screening Equipment (alcohol, narcotics...)
	Video Surveillance and Monitoring (Camera, Image Processing, Remote Control Equipment...)
Logistics for Operations - Installations	Camp Accommodation - Tents - Shelters - Temporary Installations
	CBRN Collective Protection (COLPRO)
	CBRN Decontamination
	Conditioning and Packaging (Cases...)
	Field Kitchens - Catering Equipment - Food
	Fire Detection and Alarm Systems (smoke, gas, heat detectors...)
	Generating Sets and Power Supply Systems
	Handling Equipment - Cranes - Repair Means
	Power Transportation, Distribution and Regulation
	Power, Lighting, Heating, Air-Conditioning
	Sanitary Amenities
	Storage - Resupply - Tagging / Bar Coding
	Treatment, Conditioning, and Storage of Water
	Warehouses - Installations
Medical & Emergency	First Aid and Role 1 Equipment
	Identification, Classification and Casualty Evacuation
	Medical and Surgical Equipment
	Mobile and Field Hospitals
	Protective Clothing (masks, gloves...)
	Purification - Pest Control - Decontamination
	Rescue Equipment and Desincarceration Means
Personal Equipment	Body Armor, Inserts and Protections
	Ceremonial Equipment - Medals - Uniforms
	Climbing Gear, Ladders and Hooks
	Clothing (Hairdressing, Belts, Underwear, Gloves, Shoes...)
	Decontamination Systems (CBRNe)
	Detection and Identification Systems (CBRNe)
	Diving Equipment

Activity Areas	Sub-areas
	Helmets, Visors, Masks, Ear and Eye Protection
	Individual Protective Equipment and Devices (CBRNe)
	Miscellaneous Equipment (Lamps...)
	Survival Equipment
	Tactical Jackets - Rucksacks - Pouches - Holsters
	Technical Textiles (Against Fire, Medical, Smart...)
Research, Design and Production – Materials	Ceramics
	Control, Measuring and Testing Systems
	Engineering - Design Office - Prototyping
	Fibers: Polyethylene, Aromatic, Glass
	General-Use Components and Sub-Assemblies - Treatment of Materials
	Glass
	Metals
	Plastics
	Research Institutes, Laboratories and Testing Centres
	Workshops, Tools, Automated Systems
Services	Business Continuity Consulting
	Central Purchasing
	Chambers of Commerce and Industry
	Companies of Economic and Strategic Intelligence
	Customs Broker
	Defence Exhibition and Defence-Related Events Organizers
	Demilitarization Equipment
	Document Engineering Companies
	Export Promotion Companies
	Government-Related Security Organizations (Police, Civil Defence)
	Logistics Engineering
	Manufacturers Association, Competitiveness Clusters
	Ministry / Embassy
	Non-Governmental Organizations
	Obsolescence Management
	Organization and Information Systems Consulting
	Press - Specialized Publications - Publishing - Printing
	Private Security Companies
	Quality Control - Standardization - Certification
	Recycling
	Security Risk Management Consulting
	Strategy and Management Consulting
	Teaching, Training and Protecting Organizations - Schools
	Technical Assistance and Maintenance
	Technology and Innovation Consulting
	Transport - Shipping - Handling

Activity Areas	Sub-areas
Sub-assemblies for Ground, Aerial & Naval Vehicles	Armour - Add-on Armour - Slat-Armour - Protection kits - Hardened Glass
	Camouflage - Coatings
	Cleaning (Compressors, filters...)
	Connectics, Cables
	Electrical, Electromechanical or Hydraulic Equipment
	Electronics - Vetronics - On-board Systems
	Engines and Transmission Systems - Propulsion Systems
	Fire-suppression systems
	Fuel - Lubricants - Storage - Distribution
	Naval Equipment
	Run flat and Security Devices for Pneumatics, Central Tire Inflation System (CTIS)
	Seats and Blast Mitigating Seats
	Shocks and Vibrations Mitigation
	Sub-Systems of Ground, Aerial and Naval Vehicles
	Suspension - Brakes
	Vehicle Fuel Supply Systems and Fuel Tanks
	Ventilation - Air conditioning - CBRN
Wheels - Pneumatics	
Winches	
Training & Simulation	Constructive Training Assets - Operations, Crises, Disasters Situations - Serious Games
	Firing ranges - Targets and associated equipment
	Gunnery, Driving and Piloting Simulators
	Simulated Combat Training - Convoy Trainers
	Training Aids
Training Equipment - Simulation Devices	
Weapons & Ammunitions	Air Defence Systems - Counter Rocket, Artillery, and Mortar (C-RAM)
	Air-to-Ground and Coastal Defence Systems
	Anti-tank / Wall Breaching Weapon Systems (Missiles and Rockets)
	Artillery Systems and Ammunitions (MLRS, Howitzers, Mortars, Guns)
	Close Defence Weapons - Edged Weapons, Hand Grenades and Others
	Components of Weapons
	Direct Energy Weapons (DEW)
	Fuses, Homing Heads, Guidance Systems
	Guns and Ammunition > 40 mm - Turrets
	Land mines, Explosive Charges, Firing Mechanisms
	Less-Than-Lethal or Incapacitating Systems (Launchers, Ammunition, Lasers, Hailing Systems) (Excluding lasers banned from the exhibition site)
	Medium Calibre Weapons and Ammunition (20 to 40 mm) - Turrets, Pods, Grenade Launchers, Guns & Mounts
	Propellants, Explosives, Illuminating Devices, Flares, Pyrotechnics
	Small Calibre Weapons and Ammunition < 20 mm - Pistols, Rifles, Machine Guns, Turrets, Accessories
Upgrading Weapons and Ammunition	

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